

When the Diagnosis Is Your Own: A Physician's Experience with Pneumothorax

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Abstract

Physicians are often described as poor patients, yet less attention is given to how clinical expertise may delay appropriate care. This narrative describes a physician's experience of self-diagnosed acute pneumothorax and delayed treatment, followed by radiological features suggestive of evolving tension physiology.

The account illustrates how professional identity, self-triage, and cognitive framing may influence decision-making in acute illness. It highlights the risks of delayed escalation, even among clinically experienced individuals, and underscores the need to recognize how expertise may paradoxically contribute to hesitation, making delay feel justified.

Introduction

Physicians occupy a dual role within healthcare systems as both providers of care and, at times, patients themselves. It is commonly stated that "doctors make poor patients," yet the mechanisms underlying this observation are not well defined.

Clinical expertise may paradoxically influence help-seeking behaviour, contributing to delayed presentation, self-management, and altered risk perception. Studies have shown that physicians are less likely to seek timely medical care and may under-recognise the severity of their own symptoms compared with non-medical populations (Kay et al., 2008), (Wallace et al., 2009). Cognitive biases, including overconfidence and framing effects, may further influence decision-making in acute situations (Croskerry, 2003).

Primary spontaneous pneumothorax is a relatively common acute condition, particularly among young, otherwise healthy individuals, with an incidence estimated at 7-18 per 100,000 men per year (Hallifax et al., 2018). While often initially stable, clinical progression can be unpredictable, and delayed recognition or escalation may carry significant risk.

This narrative explores these dynamics through a first-person account of spontaneous complete pneumothorax, highlighting how the boundary between clinician and patient can shift under pressure - and how that shift may impact clinical judgement.

Narrative

I was sitting at my desk between patients when the pain started. At first, it felt like something I could explain away.

A sharp pain erupted beneath my right scapula, radiating to my chest. I dismissed it as something trivial; maybe a trapped muscle from the suturing I'd just completed. I shifted, stretched, and coughed, but the pain stayed.

For several minutes, I changed positions and tried to alter my breathing, but nothing helped. Pressure built in my throat, prompting a cough. At least my airway was clear.

I joked with the nurses about everything from acute coronary syndrome to pneumothorax and gallstones. Still, I insisted it was just a muscle spasm; after all, I was just a healthy 35-year-old male. It was easier to assign a benign explanation than to escalate it.

Despite the discomfort, I tried to stay focused. Two patients were waiting, and I wanted to keep working, pushing the pain aside.

In the hallway, the pain forced me to stop and turn back. Guilt swept over me. One patient had severe shoulder pain from a fall and needed more attention, but I was walking away.

Back at the desk, one of the nurses watched me quietly.

"You seem to be in pain," she said.

Though I'm a surgeon, not a pulmonologist, I grabbed my stethoscope. The finding was unmistakable: breath sounds were absent on the right side of my chest.

I handed the stethoscope to the nurse to confirm what I thought I heard. She listened, and for the first time, her expression shifted from curiosity to concern.

I hurried down the hallway to the only other doctor, the general practitioner. He laughed, then listened. His expression matched the nurse's, and he immediately ordered a chest X-ray.

By then, the situation felt almost routine: suspected pneumothorax, imaging pending.

I made my way upstairs to radiology. When I saw the elevator was crowded, I chose the stairs and went up, two steps at a time. Halfway up, my heart pounded fiercely. My vision blurred at the edges. Then, a sudden wave of air hunger crashed over me. For the first time, the diagnosis stopped being theoretical.

Regret for choosing the stairs set in, joined by a new, raw, and unfamiliar sense of panic.

By the time I reached radiology, the dyspnoea had worsened, and the pressure in my chest had become constant.

The radiologist appeared moments later and looked at me.

"You don't look like the typical pneumothorax," he said with a smile.

I forced one back. "Am I not tall and thin?"

Two seconds later, he stopped smiling.

"I've only seen this six times before," he said.

The image was unmistakable: a complete pneumothorax. My right lung had collapsed.

Strangely, relief flooded me. A diagnosis. At last, the discomfort I had brushed aside had a name.

The guilt I felt for my patients dissolved instantly. For the first time, I accepted the role of patient.

The radiographer walked with me back toward the elevator. Downstairs, with no nurse in sight, I pulled the emergency cord in the first consultation room I passed.

"Complete pneumothorax. Transport now," I managed to say to the nurse who appeared in the hallway.

They called for an ambulance.

I had brought a large IV catheter to radiology. Back in the consultation room, I held onto it, feeling strangely alone amid sudden the activity around me.

One thought kept returning: the pneumothorax couldn't get worse by decompression.

Frightened by the progression of symptoms - the constant tightness in my chest, their rapid onset, and the growing sense of instability - I pressed my fingers against my chest, located the intercostal space, and inserted the catheter into my upper right chest.

Nothing happened. No rush of air. No immediate change.

The nurse administered oxygen as we awaited transport. The ambulance had been upgraded. Inside, I felt relief that my initial cautious judgment had been overruled for a faster transport.

On arrival at the emergency department, a chest drain was placed, and the lung re-expanded quickly overnight. I was discharged the following day.

Only later, when formal imaging report from the initial chest X-ray became available, did it describe early features suggestive of evolving tension physiology - an uncomfortable indication of how close the situation had been to further deterioration. At the time of writing, a recurrent pneumothorax has occurred, and surgical management is being considered.

It was only afterward, that I realised that clinical reasoning doesn't vanish when you're sick; if anything, it sharpens. Yet emotionally, it is far from the calm analysis we imagine when treating others.

In hindsight, I cannot say with certainty whether the needle decompression was necessary. At the time, I saw no clear signs of tension except a feeling, and the catheter itself had no obvious effect. However, the later radiology report suggested early signs of tension physiology, making any simple retrospective judgment difficult.

Still, the choice felt rational in the moment. What may seem unnecessary from the outside can feel like the safest course of action when the chest you are assessing is your own.

That day showed me how different clinical reasoning feels when you are the patient, and how quickly the boundary between physician and patient can dissolve.

Closing

What surprised me most was not the diagnosis, but the delay. Not a lack of knowledge, but the way that knowledge shaped my response.

Clinical expertise did not prevent hesitation; it reframed it, making the delay feel justified.

When the roles of physician and patient converge, judgment is no longer purely clinical. And in that space, what feels controlled may in fact be dangerously close to being delayed.

Take-home reflections

- 1 Clinical expertise may contribute to delayed presentation in acute illness
- 2 Physicians may underestimate risk when self-triaging familiar conditions
- 3 Professional identity can blur the boundary between clinician and patient
- 4 What feels like control may in fact represent delayed escalation

Declaration

I have read and understood the Authorea policy on declaration of interests and declare no competing interests.

Patient consent

The author was the patient described in this article and has provided consent for publication.

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